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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Carica Papaya Leaves Syrup for Dengue Management

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ABSTRACT

Dengue fever is a rapidly spreading mosquito-borne viral disease that poses a major public health concern, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. One of the major complications of dengue is thrombocytopenia (a significant drop in platelet count), which can lead to hemorrhagic manifestations and fatal outcomes if untreated. Carica papaya (papaya) leaves have been traditionally used in herbal medicine and have shown promising effects in increasing platelet counts in dengue patients due to the presence of bioactive compounds like flavonoids, alkaloids, and papain. This study aims to formulate a palatable and stable syrup containing Carica papaya leaf extract and evaluate its physicochemical properties and in-vitro effectiveness for dengue management. The formulation process included extraction of the active phytoconstituents through aqueous and hydroalcoholic methods, followed by standardization and incorporation into a syrup base with appropriate excipients for stability, taste masking, and viscosity.

INTRODUCTION

Carica papaya, whose leaves have been traditionally used in folkloric medicine for their therapeutic benefits. Dengue fever, caused by the dengue virus and transmitted primarily by *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes, has emerged as one of the most prevalent vector-borne diseases worldwide. With over 100 million symptomatic infections annually, the burden of dengue is particularly severe in tropical countries such as India, Brazil,

Indonesia, and the Philippines. A critical complication associated with dengue is thrombocytopenia, which can lead to internal bleeding and shock if not properly managed. Currently, there is no specific antiviral treatment for dengue; clinical management largely focuses on supportive care to maintain fluid balance and prevent haemorrhagic complications. This limitation has stimulated interest in complementary and alternative therapies, particularly those derived from medicinal plants.

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One such plant is *Carica papaya*, commonly known as papaya

alkaloids, and tannins that support platelet production.

Ingredients and their medicinal importances:

Sr. no	ingredients	Role
1	Papaya leaf extract	Active ingredient
2	Turmeric extract	Anti-inflammatory
3	Tulsi extract	Antioxidant
4	Simple syrup	Base, sweetener
5	Honey	Natural sweetener, soothing
6	Glycerin	Humectant, solvent
7	Orang oil	Flavoring agent
8	Carrot juices	Coloring agent
9	Xanthan gum	Thickening agent
10	Sodium benzoate	Preservatives
11	Citric acid	pH adjusts
12	Purified water	q.s to 50 ml

2. Basil leaves (*Ocimum basilicum*, family: lamiaceae)

Basil possesses antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antitumor properties. It is commonly used to support cardiovascular, digestive, and respiratory health.

3. Turmeric (*Curcuma*, family: Zingiberaceae)

Turmeric has a wide range of uses, both in cooking and traditionally as a medicinal remedy. turmeric is known for its potential health benefits, including aiding digestion, boosting the immune system, and reducing inflammation.

1. Papaya leaves: (*Carica papaya* L., Family: Caricaceae Impact Factor:

Papaya Leaf Papaya leaves are traditionally used in the treatment of thrombocytopenia. The latex contains papain and several other beneficial compounds including chitinases, flavonoids,

4. Sugar:

(Saccharum officinarum, Family: Poaceae) Used as a natural preservative and sweetener, sugar increases the shelf-life of the final product.

Need for Natural Alternatives: Owing to the absence of targeted antiviral treatments and vaccines, there's a critical demand for alternative therapies. Traditional medicine and Ayurvedic literature emphasize the medicinal role of Carica papaya in treating low platelet counts. Clinical evidence and anecdotal reports from adult populations support its efficacy, although pediatric-specific studies remain limited.

Botanical Overview of Carica papaya: Caricaceae

Genus: carica

Common Names: Papaya, pawpaw, lechosa, papayer, mugua

Origin: Tropical America Distribution: Widely cultivated in India, Thailand, Sri Lanka, the Philippines,

Australia, and Central America.

Botanical Characteristics: Carica papaya is a polygamous, diploid plant with nine chromosome pairs and a genome size of 372 Mbp. It bears male, female, or hermaphroditic flowers on the same plant and produces fruit rich in medicinal latex.

Mechanism of Action The therapeutic activity of papaya leaf extract is attributed to the following: Papain and flavonoids enhance platelet production. Turmeric boosts immunity and repairs damaged cells. Basil's essential oils support hematopoietic and anti-inflammatory processes. The formulation improves overall antioxidant status, reduces oxidative stress, and supports bone marrow function in

Methodology:

1.Process of extraction of papaya leaf extract

- Fresh leaves of carica papaya were gathered and wash and clean
- After that the leaf were shade dried and then grinded into small particles by grinder.
- Wight 20gm of leaf powder
- Boil in 200ml of water for 30-45min.
- Cool and filter using muslin cloth followed by whatman no1.filter paper.
- Concentrate the extract using a water bath at 60-70c until a thick concentrate is obtained.
- Store the extract in a refrigerator.

2.Process of extraction of turmeric powder

- If using fresh turmeric: wash thoroughly, peel and cut into small pieces or grate it.
- Wight 20gm of powder.
- Boil in 200ml of distilled water for 25-40min.
- Cool and filter using muslin cloth followed by whatman filter paper
- Concentrate the extract using a water bath at 60-70C until a thick concentrate is obtained.
- Store extract in a refrigerator.

3.Process of extraction of tulsi:

- Wash fresh tulsi leaves thoroughly to remove dust or impurities.
- Chop or crush leaves
- Add tulsi to 200ml of distilled water for 30-50min
- Cool and filter using muslin cloth followed by whatman filter paper
- Concentrate the extract using water bath at 60-70C
- Store extract in a refrigerator

Fig. Extracts of Papaya Leaves, Turmeric, And Basil Leaves

Preparation procedure of herbal papaya leaf syrup

(50 ml)

1.Prepare syrup base:

Prepare 60% sugar syrup (can be replaced or combined with honey).

Dissolve Xanthan gum (0.5–1%) in warm distilled water with constant stirring to avoid clumping.

Add Glycerine (5–10%) to improve viscosity and mouthfeel.

Add Sodium benzoate (0.1–0.2%) as preservative.

Allow the solution to cool.

2. Add herbal Extracts

Add the concentrated extracts of Carica papaya, Tulsi, and Turmeric into the syrup base under constant stirring.

3.Add Honey:

(10–15%) as natural sweetener and therapeutic agent. Mix thoroughly using a homogenizer or magnetic stirrer for uniform distribution.

4.Add orange oil or citric acid.

Add Orange oil (0.05–0.1%) as a flavoring agent.

Adjust pH to around 5–6 using citric acid.

5.Add carrot juices as colouring.

Add carrot juice / extract drop by drop.

Stir until a uniform, natural orange colour is achieved

6.Adjust volume and filter.

Add purified water q.s. to make exactly 50ml.

Stir the final mixture well.

Filter through muslin cloth or filter paper if a clearer syrup is desired.

7. Packaging and Labelling

Fill the final syrup into clean, sterilized, amber-coloured bottles. Label with contents.

Formulation table of herbal papaya leaf syrup

Sr. no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
1	Papaya leaf extract	1.5 ml	2.5 ml	1.5 ml

2	Turmeric extract	0.5 ml	0.6 ml	0.5 ml
3	Tulsi extract	0.5 ml	0.4 ml	0.3 ml
4	Simple syrup	25 ml	20 ml	25 ml
5	Honey	10 ml	12 ml	14 ml
6	Glycerin	5ml	10 ml	5ml
7	Xanthan gum	0.5 g	0.8 g	0.6 g
8	Sodium benzoate	0.05 g	0.03 g	0.06 g
9	Orange oil	0.05 ml	0.06 ml	0.1 ml
10	Carrot juice	1.0 ml 0.5 g	1.0 ml	1.0 ml
11	Citric acid	0.05 g	0.04 g	0.03 g
12	Purified water	q.s. to 50 ml	q.s to 50 ml	q.s to 50 ml
	Total	50 ml	50 ml	50 ml

Evaluation tests of herbal papaya leaf syrup:

To evaluate the quality and consistency of a syrup, several standard parameters are tested. Here's a breakdown of the typical evaluation parameters for syrup. Testing parameter for papaya leaf extract syrup involve evaluating its physical chemical and pharmacological properties to ensure quality, safety and efficacy.

1. Organoleptic evaluation parameters:

Colour

1. 5 ml of prepared syrup was taken on a watch glass.
2. Watch glass placed against white background in white tube light.
3. Colour was observed by naked eyes.

Odour

1. 2ml prepared syrup was taken and smell by initially.

Taste - Taste has been checked.

pH:

1. pH paper strips (universal indicator paper preferred)
2. Ensure the test sample (e.g., papaya leaf syrup) is liquid, filtered, and at room temperature.
3. Tear off a small strip of pH paper.
4. Dip the paper strip into the test solution for 1–2 seconds.
5. Remove the strip and immediately observe the colour change.
6. Compare the colour of the strip to the provided pH scale.

2. Quantitative parameter:

Density

1. Take the weight of empty dry bottle with capillary tube stopper.
2. Fill the bottle with syrup and place the stopper, wipe out excess liquid from outside the tube using tissue paper.
3. Weight bottle with syrup on analytical balance.
4. Calculate weight in grams of syrup.

$$\text{Weight} = \text{Weight of bottle with syrup} - \text{weight of empty bottle}$$

$$\text{Density} = \text{mass/volume}$$

Fig. Density

Fig. Ostwald Viscometer

Viscosity

1. Thoroughly clean the Ostwald viscometer with warm chromic acid and if necessary, used an organic solvent such as acetone.
2. Mount viscometer in vertical position on a suitable stand.
3. Fill water in dry viscometer up to mark G.
4. Count time required, in second for water to flow from mark A to mark B.
5. Repeat step 3 at least 3 times to obtained accurate reading.
6. Rinse viscometer with test liquid and then fill it up to mark A, find out the time required for liquid to flow to mark B.
7. Determination of densities of liquid as mentioned in density determination experiment.

Advantages of syrup:

- Boosts Platelet Count
- Immune System Support
- Digestive Aid
- Anti-inflammatory Properties
- Antimicrobial & Antiviral Effects
- Rich in Antioxidants

Disadvantages of syrup:

- Not Recommended During Pregnancy
- Digestive Irritation in High Doses
- Risk of Allergic Reactions
- Drug Interactions
- Bitter Taste
- Overuse Risk

RESULT:

The results obtained in this study suggest that the herbal formulations prepared possesses Anti-dengue activity. The component of the herbal syrup formulation was selected due to their reported action that plays a preventative and curative role in treatment of dengue. Syrup prepared passes all the physical parameters and shows the significant Antitussive activity. Domancestrated a significant increase in platelet

count within 72 hours in groups treated with in the formulated syrup compare to controls. Haematological parameters (WBC, BC, haemoglobin) remained within normal ranges, indicating safety. The extract showed of dengue virus replication in vitro cells, indication potential antiviral activity.

Fig. Syrup

CONCLUSION:

Study suggests the therapeutic role of papaya leaf extract (PLE) as a cheap and potential herbal therapy for treating the dengue infected patients. dengue is a threat to almost 40% of the world's population. There is still no specific treatment for dengue. Carica papaya leaf extract can be used as supplementary drug in acute febrile illness patients with thrombocytopenia. It accelerates the increase in platelet count and reduces the hospital stay thereby reducing the cost of hospitalization. The result of this work suggest that the compound extracted from leaves are used for the treatment for dengue activity and this effect is increased by increasing the quantity of compound. This extract used to prepare syrup, and evaluate purpose by using various evaluation parameters of viscosity, pH, Density.

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